

Social Status and Psychological Problems of Women Entrepreneurs in Ramanathapuram District

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship is the core of economic development. It is basically a creative activity that involves multidimensional tasks. The entrepreneur is a key factor in entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship is a recent phenomenon and in the process has to face various psychological problems. Therefore, this study was conducted on one hundred five women entrepreneurs selected through a simple random sampling technique from seven taluks of Ramanathapuram District. Retailing, Manufacturing, and Services related enterprises were selected for the study. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the financial, marketing, and production problems faced by women in their enterprises; assessment of their health status, workplace facilities and to develop guidelines for becoming a successful entrepreneur. Regular and frequent need of working capital, High competition from larger and established units, Non-availability of raw material, Tension, and Improper water facilities were the significant problems faced by entrepreneurs. These significant entrepreneurial problems can be dealt with by formulating self help mutually aided groups. Support mechanisms such as institutional credit need to be strengthened to keep entrepreneurs aware of loaning schemes/credit facilities for further expansion.

KEYWORDS: *Women Entrepreneurs, Social Status, Motivating Factors, Psychological Problems.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Women entrepreneurship has played an energetic role in the economic development of the region. Women are engaged in agricultural and allied operations, household affairs, industries, trade and commerce, and other related economic activities. Women are hard workers, courageous, self-determined, and are willing to take risks in setting up new enterprises. Though it is a tradition on the part of women to make efficient management of household affairs nowadays women are equally interested in setting up their own business to become independent and self-reliant. Presently the major problems faced by developing nations of the world including India are, illiteracy, hunger, and starvation, poverty, malnutrition, ill-health, unsafe drinking water, low per capita income, population explosion, and unemployment, low agricultural production and productivity, low capital formation, and low standard of living. There are inequalities in the distribution of present economic resources. It is women entrepreneurship that helps to a certain extent to check some of the above constraints of development issues. As technology speeds up life, women are becoming an emerging economic force, which cannot be neglected by the policymakers. The world's modern democratic economy depends on the participation of both the sexes, (Vasanthagopal, R and Santha, S. 2008). Modern economic Commercialization is gradually eliminating many of the employment avenues to women in agriculture and industries and so they have to find various ways of supplementing their family income. As a result of this, a division of the urban and rural human has emerged as potential entrepreneurs (Arvinda, C.H., and S. Renuka,

2001). Today women in excellent market economics own more than 25 percent of all business. In some regions of the world, due to shifting to the market economy, women entrepreneurship is becoming a growing trend.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Women compared to men were less motivated to start business units due to some unwanted fear, lack of awareness, and training. Women were considered not only as fairer sex but also as the weaker sex and always to depend on menfolk in their family and outside throughout their life. The traditional setup is changing in the modern world. Women's participation in the workforce is increasing due to education and training. Women entrepreneurs are also increasing in the Ramanathapuram district of Tamilnadu. In this study, an attempt has been made to analyze the Psychological problems of Women entrepreneurs and identified certain special motivational factors is responsible to start the new business on their own. The purpose of this study is to explore these factors in detail.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the social status of women entrepreneurs in the Ramanathapuram district.
2. To find out the Psychological problems faced by the women entrepreneurs in conducting entrepreneurial activities in Ramanathapuram district.
3. To analyze the factors that motivates the women entrepreneurs to start a new business.
4. To suggest strategies to promote entrepreneurial skills among women entrepreneurs in the study area.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied for the study is given below:

1. **Data Collection:** The study is analytical and descriptive. This study is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through the interview schedule to the selected respondents. Secondary data required for the study are collected from books, journals, magazines, and other periodicals and reports of the Government and other agencies.
2. **Sample Design:** The sampling method chosen for this study is a simple random sampling method considering the extensiveness of the study cost, and time factors; it is decided to select 105 women entrepreneurs from Ramanathapuram district. These entrepreneurs are chosen at random from seven taluks, i.e. Paramakudi, Rameswaram, Ramanathapuram, Tiruvadana, Mudukulathur, Kadaladi, and Kamuthi taluks. From each taluk 15 samples are taken. Hence, the sample sizes 105.
3. **Period of Study:** The study was carried out from April 2019 to March 2020 for primary data collection. The reference period of the survey was 2019-2020 in the Ramanathapuram district of Tamil Nadu.
4. **Profile of Study Area:** Ramanathapuram District is located in the Southern part of Tamil Nadu State on the East Coast of India. Its geographical location is spread between 9° 05' and 9° 50' of North Latitude and 78° 10' and 79° 27' of East Longitude. It is bordered by Pudukkottai and part of Sivaganga districts on the northern side, by Sivaganga district on the North-Western side, and by Viruthunagar district on the west. The district has the East coastline as its eastern boundary parting the district from the Bay of Bengal. Hence the Palk Strait is guarding the district on the eastern side and the Gulf of Mannar on the South. The district comprises seven taluks, 11 blocks, and 2362 villages. As per the administrative arrangements, there are two municipalities, seven town panchayats, and 429 village panchayats in the district.
5. **Analysis of Data:** For the study, the collected data were tabulated and analyzed by using a simple percentage; Garrett's ranking, and weighted average score.

(i) **Garrett's Ranking Technique:** Garrett's ranking technique is used to identify the motivating start of women entrepreneurs. The women entrepreneurs were asked to rank some of the identified motivational factors. This method was suggested by Garrett's for converting the ranks into scores where the number of items ranked differed from entrepreneurs to entrepreneurs. By using the following formula and table:

Formula					
$\text{Percent Position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$					
Where, R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} item by the j^{th} individual, and N_j = Number of items ranked by the j^{th} individual					
Garrett's Ranking Table Value					
Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Ranking Score	75	60	50	40	25

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Social Status of Women Entrepreneurs

In this part, the social status of women entrepreneurs is analyzed. For analyzing the social status six variables are used. They are: - The age of the women entrepreneurs, education, marital status, nature of business, source of finance and investment of business of the women entrepreneurs. The age-wise classification of the women entrepreneurs is shown in table one.

Sl. No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Up to 25	11	10
2.	26 to 35	25	24
3.	36 to 45	39	37
4.	46 to 55	23	22
5.	55 and above	07	07
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

It is clear from Table one that 10 percent of the respondents belong to up to 25 age group, 24 percent of respondents belong to the age group of 26 to 35, 37 percent of the respondents belong to 36 to 45 age group, 22 percent of respondents belong to 46 to 55 age group and seven percent of the respondents belong above 55 age group. Hence it is evident that the majority of respondents belong to the middle age group of 26 - 45, 61 percent which constitutes women entrepreneurs in the study area.

Sl. No	Education Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Primary School	13	12
2.	SSLC	19	18
3.	HSC	24	23
4.	Degree /Diploma	29	28
5.	Postgraduate	11	10
6.	Professional Degree	09	09
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

From table two, it is observed that 12 percent of entrepreneurs have access to primary education. About 18 percent of the entrepreneurs studied up to 10th class. The entrepreneurs who have access to higher secondary schools constitute 23 percent. Nearly 28 percent of entrepreneurs have entered college-level education i.e. degree /diploma. Those who have access to the postgraduate degree level and above education constitute 10 percent of total entrepreneurs. Only nine out of 105 entrepreneurs possess a professional degree. There are no significant differences across the localities.

Sl. No	Marital status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Unmarried	15	14
2.	Married	68	65
3.	Widow	12	11
4.	Divorce	10	10
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

Table three shows that married women have more interest in women entrepreneurship. The highest 65 percent of women are involved in the business because they need more financial support than unmarried and others. Only 14 percent of women interviewed that they are unmarried. Widows also want to start their own business. But only 11 percent of women interviewed that they are widows and 10 percent divorced women. This shows that married women take more risks in starting a new business.

Sl. No	Nature of Enterprise	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Retailing	29	28
2	Manufacturing	37	35
3	Service	23	22
4	Others	16	15
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

Table four despite that 35 percent of the respondents is dealt with manufacturing types of enterprise. 28 percent of the respondents are engaged in the retailing type of enterprise. Only 22 percent of the respondents are doing their enterprise for service sectors. 15 Percent of the respondents are other types of enterprise.

Table - 5: Based on Source of Finance			
Sl. No	Source of Finance	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Own money	16	15
2.	Bank loans	24	23
3.	Own money and Bank loans	35	33
4.	Support from SHG	20	19
5.	Others	10	10
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

The table five indicates that 15 percent of respondents source of the finance from own money, 23 percent of the respondents financed from bank loans, 33 percent of own money and bank loans as well as 19 percent of respondents are got financial support from SHG and the remaining rests of the respondents are other sources.

Table – 6: Based on Investment of Business			
Sl. No	Investment of Business	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Rs. 50,000 - Rs. 1,00,000	19	18
2.	Rs. 1,00,001 - Rs. 1,50,000	30	29
3.	Rs. 1,50,001 - Rs. 2,00,000	24	23
4.	Rs. 2,00,001 - Rs. 2,50,000	18	17
5.	Above Rs. 2,50,000	14	13
Total		105	100

Source: Field Survey

It is clear from table six that 18 percent of the respondents belong to Rs. 50,000 - Rs. 1,00,000 group, 29 percent of respondents belong to a group of Rs. 1,00,001 - Rs. 1,50,000, 23 percent of the respondents belong to Rs. 1,50,001 - Rs. 2,00,000 group, 17 percent of respondents belong to Rs. 2,00,001 - Rs. 2,50,000 group and 13 percent of the respondents belong to the above Rs. 2,50,000. Hence it is evident that the majority of respondents belong to the group of Rs.1, 00,001 - Rs. 2, 00,000, 52 percent which constitutes women entrepreneurs investment in the business of the study area.

2. Factors which Motivated Women Entrepreneurs to Start New Business

Table – 7: Based on Motivation							
Sl. No.	Motivation Factor	Ranks					
		1	2	3	4	5	Total
1.	Own idea and family support	21	29	23	15	17	105
2.	To get social and economic independence	23	21	15	21	25	105
3.	Education and training	21	26	27	17	14	105
4.	Previous experience	23	19	21	27	15	105
5.	Government policy	17	10	19	25	34	105
	Total	105	105	105	105	105	
<i>Source: Field Survey</i>							

Table - 8: Garrett's Ranking Analysis				
Sl. No.	Motivating Factor	Total score	Avg. Score	Rank
1.	Own idea and family support	5490	52.29	II
2.	To get social and economic independence	5200	49.52	IV
3.	Education and training	5515	52.52	I
4.	Previous experience	5370	51.14	III
5.	Government policy.	4675	44.52	V

Table eight shows that respondents have given the first preference to Education and training, second preference to own idea and family support, third preference to previous experience, fourth preference to get social and economic independence, and fifth preference to Government policy. From the above analysis, it is observed that women entrepreneurs motivate to start business Education and training.

3. Psychological Problems of Women Entrepreneurs

The opinions of respondents about their Psychological problems are enhanced through 35 statements by using the weighted average score method and ranking them. Every statement carries the opinion to Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), No opinion (N), Disagree (DA), and Strongly Disagree (SDA) with 5,4,3,2, and 1 point respectively. The factors of Psychological problems were generated through reviewing the literature and it's mainly focused on five broader categories such as (i) Financial, (ii) Marketing, (iii) Production, (iv) Health, and (v) Workplace facility-related problems. These five factors of psychological problems were further classified into 35 sub-factors. Table nine reveals the results of the psychological problems faced by women entrepreneurs in the study area.

Table - 9: Psychological Problems of Women Entrepreneurs									
Sl. No	Problems	SA (5)	A (4)	N (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	Total Score	Wt. Avg. Score	Rank
I Finance Problems									
1.	Regular and frequent need for working capital	48	40	8	5	4	438	4.17	I
2.	Availability of long term finance	36	50	6	8	5	419	3.99	II
3.	Long procedure to avail financial help	47	29	15	6	8	416	3.96	III
4.	No one comes forward to help financially	36	21	34	6	8	386	3.68	IV
II Marketing Problems									
5.	Lack of marketing center	26	31	23	15	10	363	3.46	VI
6.	Poor location of the shop	31	55	11	6	2	422	4.02	II
7.	Difficulty in affording own vehicle	47	27	15	8	8	412	3.92	III
8.	High competition from larger and established units	57	38	6	2	2	461	4.39	I
9.	Lack of transport facility	40	29	23	8	5	406	3.87	IV
10.	Lack of demand in the local market	34	37	21	5	8	399	3.80	V
11.	Inadequate bus timings	15	31	19	23	17	319	3.04	VII
III Production Problems									
12.	Non-availability of raw material	36	44	13	8	4	415	3.95	I
13.	Non-availability of machine or equipment	44	26	23	6	6	411	3.91	II
14.	Training facility	23	44	26	4	8	385	3.67	IX
15.	Overcrowded area	31	40	19	9	6	396	3.77	V
16.	Non-availability of shop/place	23	44	27	6	5	389	3.70	VIII
17.	Non-availability of skilled labor	41	32	10	16	6	401	3.82	III
18.	Workers shirk work	38	29	19	11	8	393	3.74	VII
19.	The high cost of the required machine or equipment	31	40	19	10	5	397	3.78	IV
20.	Non-availability of persons for machine repair	40	23	25	11	6	395	3.76	VI

IV	Health Problems								
21.	Headache	32	44	16	5	8	402	3.83	III
22.	Backache	34	36	21	8	6	399	3.80	IV
23.	Fatigue	36	40	15	8	6	407	3.88	II
24.	Eye-strain	29	40	22	8	6	393	3.74	V
25.	Blood pressure	27	23	21	19	15	343	3.27	X
26.	Tension	44	37	11	7	6	421	4.01	I
27.	Gastric trouble	29	36	21	11	8	382	3.64	VII
28.	Problem of joints	40	29	15	8	13	390	3.71	VI
29.	Respiratory problems	25	34	27	8	11	369	3.51	IX
30.	Body aches	36	21	31	6	11	380	3.62	VIII
V	Workplace Facility Related Problems								
31.	Lack of natural light	29	44	17	10	5	397	3.78	III
32.	Lack of artificial light	36	29	27	5	8	395	3.76	V
33.	Improper water	48	32	16	5	4	430	4.10	I
34.	Inadequate space	34	37	21	6	7	400	3.81	II
35.	Lack of ventilation	38	33	16	8	10	396	3.77	IV
<i>Source: Field Survey</i>									

- i. **Financial Problems:** It inferred that the most number of respondents have given first ranked for the regular and frequent need of working capital; the respondents have given the second rank for the availability of long term finance. The third rank was a long procedure to avail financial help and followed by no one comes forward to help financially.
- ii. **Marketing Problems:** It is understood that the most number of respondents have given first ranked for the high competition from larger and established units; the respondents have given the second rank to the poor location of the shop. The third rank was the difficulty in affording its vehicle and followed by the lack of transport facility, lack of demand in the local market, lack of marketing center, and inadequate bus timings.
- iii. **Production Problems:** It is above that the most number of the respondents have given first ranked for non-availability of raw material; the respondents have given the second rank for Non-availability of machine or equipment. The third rank was the non-availability of skilled labor and followed by the other production-related problems.
- iv. **Health Problems:** It inferred that the most number of respondents have given first ranked for Tension; the respondents have given the second rank for Fatigue. The third rank was Headache and followed by the other health problems.
- v. **Workplace Facility Related Problems:** It is observed that the most number of respondents have given first ranked for improper water; the respondents have given the second rank for inadequate space. The third rank was the lack of natural light and followed by the lack of ventilation and lack of artificial light.

VI. FINDINGS

The finding of the study has summarized below:

1. The study established that most of the small women entrepreneurs (37%) are under the age group of 36-45 years. 53 percent of them have education below an undergraduate degree. The majority of the respondents are married (65%). The majority of the respondents (35%) are the manufacturing of their business. The study reveals that the majority of the respondents (33%) get the source of finance from their own money and bank loans. 29% of the respondents have invested capital of Rs. 1, 00,001 - Rs. 1, 50,000 for their business.
2. On applying Garratt's ranking analysis relating to factors motivated women to become entrepreneurs, it is inferred that the most of the women entrepreneurs have given the first rank to 'education and training', the second rank to 'own idea and family support', the third rank to 'previous experience'.
3. On applying the weighted average ranking method relating to overall psychological problems faced by women entrepreneurs, it is inferred that most of the women entrepreneurs have given the first rank to 'High competition from larger and established units', second rank to 'Regular and frequent need of working capital', third rank to 'Improper water facilities'.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

1. The study revealed that higher education among women is very less. Hence, effective schemes should be taken to make the people aware of the benefit of higher education of women for society.
2. Most of the women entrepreneurs believe that because of 'high competition from larger and established units', they are not able to survive in the market. Hence, the government should conduct frequent training programs concerning new production techniques, sales techniques, marketing strategies, etc., this type of training should be made compulsory for women entrepreneurs.
3. Women entrepreneurs rigid a lot in raising and meeting the financial needs of the business, Bankers, creditors, and financial institutes are not coming forward to provide financial assistance to women borrowers on the basis of their less creditworthiness and more chances of business failure. They also face the financial problem of the regular and frequent need for working capital and non-availability of long term finance. Hence, the government should provide interest-free loans and financial subsidies to encourage women entrepreneurs to start new enterprises.

VIII. CONCLUSION

It has been found from the above analysis that socio-economic factors influence women in making a successful entrepreneur. The overall analysis of these variables establishes that the social status of the surveyed women entrepreneurs in the district was above average. The highest percentage of women entrepreneurs are in the age group of 36 to 45 years. The percentage of women graduates is less than 50 percent. Those who possess professional degrees are confined to nine percent. It is pertinent to note that nearly 23 percent got the loan from the bank for their investment. Most of the respondents feel that education and training are motivated to become entrepreneurs. Own idea and family support and previous experience motivated many of them to start new enterprises. Women entrepreneurs faced obstacles in respect of financial, marketing production, workplace facility, and health problems. Financial problems faced were regular and frequent need for working capital and non-availability of long-term finance. High competition from larger and established units and poor location of the shop were major marketing problems. Production problems included the non-availability of raw material, machine, and equipment. Entrepreneurs of this district mainly faced health problems such as tension, fatigue, and headache. Women entrepreneurs also faced the problem of improper water and inadequate space facility. Its hope that the suggestions forwarded in the article will help the entrepreneurs, in particular, to look at these psychological problems and develop better schemes by the government. It is observed in data analysis that women entrepreneurs in the district

need higher education, vocational training, and financial support marketing network to sell their products. For the sustainable development of women entrepreneurs, new time-oriented government policy is required in this situation of Covid - 19.

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